

FACTORS AFFECTING THE FORMATION OF QUALITIES OF MORAL AND ETHICAL RESPONSIBILITY IN A PERSON

Turaxonov Abdugarim Eshkuziyevich

Surkhandarya region national center for training pedagogues in new methods, Head of the educational process organization department, philosophy doctor on psychology (PhD)
Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy, Psychology and Educational Technologies
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8301385>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the topic of factors influencing the formation of a person's qualities of moral and ethical responsibility. The text of the article also highlights the psychological components that ensure the formation of professional responsibility, and the psychological characteristics that determine the professional responsibility of students.*

Keywords: *moral and ethical responsibility, psychological characteristics, students.*

The formation of professional responsibility in students is considered a very complex process, and many psychological and pedagogical measures are currently being implemented in connection with the development of its model. However, the theoretical and practical study of this problem in the local environment still requires advanced psychological research. Because professional responsibility is formed not only by the educational process, but also by the student's personal value system, the content of the emotional and volitional sphere, the development of the cognitive sphere, carefully mastered skills and competencies that ensure professional success, work on the formation of qualities such as professional skills and professional competence is envisaged. In our opinion, the successful organization of training sessions in the conditions of higher education is the first step in the formation of professional responsibility.

According to Yu.G. Tatur, the formation of a sense of professional responsibility is inextricably linked with the rules of organizing successful training, and the main factor is educational motivation and internal mental capabilities of students. The more interesting the lessons are, the higher the motivation of the students. The students of the first stage of the university are more sensitive, curious and active to the information of the field. After passing to the second stage, the level of self-management in the educational environment, resistance to any difficulties in educational activities, and the level of responsibility for tasks are significantly increased. He states that students' creative abilities to perform tasks are fully formed after passing to the third stage. Contrary to these opinions, according to A.K. Markova, the manifestation of professional responsibility is a transition to professionalism, which is explained by the following features:

1. Professional performance characteristics - high productivity and efficiency;
2. Knowledge, abilities and skills of the subject of activity - professional skills, thinking style, level of intuition, independence in solving professional problems, high-level qualifications and professional competences;
3. Individual psychological qualities of the subject of activity - the possibility of developing labor relations as an individual, the presence of goals of positive social significance;
4. Self-change through professional direction - mastering the requirements of professional activity, professional ethical norms, moral norms, etc.;

5. The ability to adapt oneself to the profession and the profession to oneself, the ability to cooperate;

6. Possessing characteristics that describe a person's state - positive self-awareness, knowing one's own worth: the predominance of a positive mood, satisfaction with one's profession, perception of oneself as an expert, stability of professional motivation, experience based decision making ability etc.

V.I. Slobodchikov said that the qualities of personality specific to professional activity formed in students reflect the nature of responsibility in their content, and this is clearly manifested in the activities of successful students. Professional activity requires a certain set of personal qualities and abilities from future specialists, through which the future capabilities of a person are evaluated. As a result of mastering theoretical and practical knowledge necessary for the field, important qualities of professional importance begin to appear in a person.

While researching the issue of responsibility, O. N. Shaldibina, according to his conclusions, students studying social and humanitarian fields are ready for any communication situation, have the skills of emotional self-control in relationships, and others. are educational subjects who can attract, combine their interests with the interests of others, and have high intellectual abilities. So, it is confirmed that, in contrast to students in the natural direction, the formation of socio-psychological competencies that ensure professional responsibility is at a high level in the students of the socio-humanitarian direction.

It should be noted that the formation of professional responsibility is a dynamic phenomenon that requires constant activity. That is, timely support and encouragement of successful students is considered very important.

Researcher J. Rotter, as a mature representative of the doctrine of "Social learning", offers to consider the manifestation of professional responsibility in two cases:

- Responsibility in the first case - a person considers himself responsible for everything that happens in his life. And this is called the place of internal control, subjective mechanism in a person. That is, each person is responsible for his profession, family, life path. At the same time, people are responsible for their successes and failures. People of this type are considered to have an internal locus of control mechanism (searching for reasons). These ideas were further improved in practical terms by Russian psychologists V.V. Ctolin and C.R. Pantelyev. Currently, the test "Determining the level of subjective control in a person" developed and modified by them is used as a research method in many modern studies.

- In the second case, responsibility - a person blames external people for failures and other important events that he could not achieve. That is, parents, teachers, relatives, conditions, etc. It is clear from this that the sense of responsibility is not only a feature that determines the maturity of a person, but also a concept that describes self-awareness, awareness of one's duty.

Foreign researcher D.I. Feldstein explains the criteria for being responsible in activities by:

- Experience of self-management or self-regulation through accepted norms and rules;
- Acquired emotional experience, competence based on cooperation and the ability to work on the formed self;
- Self-management skills in activities and difficult situations.

Contrary to the above classifications, according to psychologist A.V. Petrovsky, there are two aspects that determine the manifestation of responsibility in educational activities:

- External conditions that develop personal responsibility, i.e., a modern higher educational institution, experienced professors and teachers with high potential, training manuals and textbooks created in the field, field or the connection of the complaint with the practice, etc.

- Internal opportunities that ensure the manifestation of a sense of responsibility in students
 - level of satisfaction of social needs, interest in studying, level of professional motivation, worldview, professional thinking, etc.

According to C.F. Anisimov, N.A. Golovko, one of the researchers, professional responsibility is a set of specific actions of a person, in which there is an attitude phenomenon based on the external environment and mutual relations. In addition, C.F. Anisimov said that two aspects of the analysis of professional responsibility are distinguished:

- The objective side of the responsibility is the general requirements imposed by the educational institution on the subjects of education;

- The subjective side of responsibility is self-sacrifice, conscientiousness and commitment to professional values or awareness of one's duties, characteristic of an exemplary person. Therefore, the formation of professional responsibility develops not only with requirements, educational methods, but also with internal procedures - rules.

Taking into account the scientific research, views, and opinions of the above-mentioned research scientists, we conducted a survey among students "Study of the qualities of moral and ethical responsibility of the individual" and analyzed the results.

Table 1

Analysis of the results of the questionnaire "Study of the qualities of moral and ethical responsibility of a person"

Scales M Student-t	Scales M Student-t	Scales M Student-t
Reflection	2,44	0,78**
Moral and ethical responsibility	2,39	0,80**
Existential responsibility	2,76	0,77**
Altruistic responsibility	3,09	0,76**
Moral and ethical values	2,76	0,77**
Sincerity	2,78	0,78**

Note: ** $r \leq 0.01$.

We can see that the students achieved a high overall score on the results of this survey. According to the standard norm, reflection on the first scale made a total high difference. The conditions created in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in students create opportunities for independent development of personal qualities for students, as well as the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities to be an example to young people in the future and to form and develop reflexive skills in them. can serve to form skills. When modeling the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in students, it is necessary to take into account the unique aspects of person-oriented education and the creation of opportunities to ensure the improvement of their personal qualities in educational processes. The next scale is high in moral-ethical responsibility, and moral responsibility is historically formed in a particular society and serves social development and personal development.

In other words, positive moral-ethical responsibility is a specific practical expression of human behavior, more precisely, of human moral perfection. As the level of moral and ethical

responsibility increases, its positive aspects become valuable. According to the scale of existential responsibility, it means that students' values are high and their capabilities are developed at a normal level. High existential responsibility makes a person accept life situations and difficulties easily and positively. The next scale shows that altruistic responsibility is higher than average in students, and an altruistic person puts social interests above personal interests, and they have socially desirable behaviors, social responsibility, feeling responsible for their actions, and emotional self. characteristics such as self-control will be formed. In students who are prone to altruistic behavior, the presence of social responsibility, the ability to see the solution to the problem, the formation of moral and legal consciousness, social support of others and the averageness of social perception are clearly visible. According to the scale of moral and ethical values, the students scored above the average, which indicates that they have developed moral values. The next scale is determined by the fact that sincerity is above average and that they understand the essence of the questionnaire sufficiently. The high difference in these results indicates the dispersion of the groups. Therefore, by developing psychological characteristics such as reflection, moral-ethical responsibility, altruistic responsibility, moral-ethical values, problem solving, critical thinking, internal local control, responsibility, initiative, tenacity and enthusiasm in students. responsibility efficiency is ensured. Also, the level of moral-ethical responsibility of a person, the stability of professional will-responsibility, the uniqueness of coping qualities and the direction of subjective local control, which are manifested in the formation of professional responsibility of students, contribute to the strengthening of future professional activity, stable and consistent serves to ensure its development.

REFERENCES

1. Анисимов Е.В. История России от Рюрика до Путина: люди, события, даты / Е.В.Анисимов. – 2-е изд., доп. – Санкт-Петербург: Питер, 2010. – 571 с.
2. Головки Е.А. Технология формирования коммуникативной компетентности молодых специалистов вуза на этапе адаптации к педагогической деятельности [Текст]: автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук: 13.00.08 / Е.А.Головки. – Ставрополь, 2004. – 20 с.
3. Маркова А.К. Психология профессионализма. М. 2-Изд. Юнайт, 2004.– 308 с.
4. Петровский А.В. Психология: учебник для студентов высших учебных заведений, обучающихся по педагогическим специальностям / А.В.Петровский, М.Г.Ярошевский. – Москва: Академия, 1998. – 500 с.
5. Слободчиков В.И. Психология развития человека: развитие субъективной реальности в онтогенезе: учеб. пособие для вузов / В.И.Слободчиков, Е.И.Исаев. – М.: Школьная Пресса, 2000 – 416 с.
6. Татур Ю.Г. Компетентность в структуре модели качества подготовки специалиста / Ю.Г.Татур // Высшее образование сегодня. – 2004. – №3. – С. 13 - 18.
7. Фельдштейн Д.И. Возрастная и педагогическая психология: Избранные психологические труды. – М.: МПСИ, 2012. – 427 с.
8. Шалдыбина О.Н. Проблема ответственности в отечественной психологии Текст. / О.Н.Шалдыбина // Вестник Самарского государственного педагогического университета. Психология. Самара: СГПУ, 2007 - 2008. – С. 47 - 54.
9. Rotter J.B., and Mulry R.C. Internal versus external control of reinforcement and decision time. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 2008. – 634 p.